

5-YEAR REVIEW

California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*)

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GENERAL INFORMATION:

Species: California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*)

Date listed: October 13, 1970

FR citation(s): 35 FR 16047

Classification: Endangered

BACKGROUND:

Most recent status review:

The most recent 5-year review of California clapper rail was finalized on April 29, 2013 (2013 5-Year Review; U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service [USFWS, Service] 2013a). A notice announcing initiation of that 5-year review of this taxon and the opening of a 60-day period to receive information from the public was published in the Federal Register on May 21, 2010 (75 FR 28636). We received no comment letters in response to the Federal Register Notice. That review did not result in a change in the status of the species.

FR Notice citation announcing this status review:

FR citation: 83 FR 28251 28254

Title: Endangered and Threatened Wildlife and Plants; Initiation of 5-Year Status Reviews of 50 Species in California, Nevada, and the Klamath Basin of Oregon. **AGENCY:** Fish and Wildlife Service, Interior. **ACTION:** Notice of initiation of reviews; request for information,

Date of notice: June 18, 2018

Comments received: We received one comment letter (Jones 2018) in response to the Federal Register Notice. The letter recommended no status change for the California clapper rail and did not provide any information beyond what is available to the Service for use in this status review.

ASSESSMENT:

Introduction

This 5-year review was conducted by the USFWS San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office (BDFWO). Data for this review were solicited from interested parties through a Federal Register notice announcing this review on June 18, 2018. Additionally, we conducted a literature search and review of information in our files. Based on our inspection of the last 5-year review and available new information, we believe the most recent status review is still an accurate representation or assessment of the status of the species, its biology, and the threats affecting it. In our review of progress toward recovery criteria (USFWS 2013b), because the primary population spatial distribution and abundance thresholds prescribed in downlisting criterion E/1 for specified average number of rails over a 10-year period by recovery unit have not been achieved (see *Population Spatial Distribution and Abundance* discussion below), we did not review progress toward other criterion. Based on our analysis, the status of the California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) (CCR; rail) remains endangered and we did not revise the recovery priority number of 3C. The priority number of 3C is based on a high degree of threat, a high potential of recovery, and its taxonomic standing as a subspecies. The additional “C”

ranking indicates some degree of conflict between the conservation needs of the species and economic development (USFWS 1983).

Information Acquired Since the Last Status Review

Note Regarding Taxonomic and Nomenclature

Based on the work of Maley and Brumfield (2013), the American Ornithologist's Union (AOU) Committee on Classification and Nomenclature accepted in its 55th Supplement to the AOU Check-list of North American Birds (Chesser *et al* 2014), revisions to the specific assignments under the genus *Rallus*. Among those changes, the species *R. obsoletus* (Ridgway's rail) and *R. crepitans* (Clapper rail) were split from *R. longirostris*, and *R. longirostris* was deleted.

The AOU Check-list of North American Birds has not addressed subspecies treatments since its 5th edition was published in 1957. Rather, the AOU refers to the listing of the Birds of North America by the Cornell Lab of Ornithology for subspecies treatments. In its subspecies treatments for *R. obsoletus* (Eddelman and Conway 2018), the Cornell Lab of Ornithology included a change from California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) to California Ridgway's Rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*).

Until a time when the USFWS formally adopts the taxonomic and nomenclature changes described above, the USFWS maintains the use of California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) as used in this current 5-year review.

Population and Habitat Distribution and Abundance

The 2013 5-Year Review and the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California* (Recovery Plan; USFWS 2013b) reviewed that multiple factors influence the California clapper rail population. In our current analysis of the population status, we reviewed new information about the spatial distribution and abundance of rails, the area characterized as suitable habitat associated with rail surveys, and possible relationships among these ecological parameters. Below we explain: (1) our *Methods* and then present our analysis and conclusions in two parts, (2) *Population Spatial Distribution and Abundance*, and (3) *Habitat Spatial Distribution and Abundance*.

Methods

There is currently no USFWS BDFWO range-wide California clapper rail monitoring program or protocol nor habitat suitability metrics available to evaluate recovery progress of the species and its habitat. Developing a range-wide robust and coordinated monitoring program and a habitat assessment and modeling protocol are high priorities for the USFWS BDFWO. In this current 5-year review, we used the best available information to evaluate population and habitat status and trend, as described below.

Our Data

The 2013 5-Year Review and the Recovery Plan considered population and habitat information through approximately 2011 and referenced an abundance estimate from Liu *et al* (2009). For our current analysis, we did not reference contemporary published abundance estimates of others because none exist. Since census data is not available, we used reported site-level California clapper rail call count survey data and habitat assessment information from 2005-2018 as indices of population abundance and trend. Our review predominantly used rail survey data and habitat assessment information from the San Francisco Estuary Invasive Spartina Project (ISP) as reported for the *USFWS formal endangered species consultation on the San Francisco Estuary Invasive Spartina Project* (2012 Biological Opinion; USFWS File No: 08ESMF00-2012-F-0584-xx) from McBroom (2014, 2015, 2016, 2018, 2019), McBroom *et al* (2011), ISP (2015, 2016a, 2016b), and the USFWS (2011, 2012, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017). The ISP began in 2000 and the 2012 Biological Opinion included rail survey data beginning in 2005. The geographic scope of the ISP during our period of analysis was approximately 50,000 acres of tidal marsh, including both rail habitat and non-rail habitat (USFWS 2012 and 2017). The area of rail habitat is further described below and in the sections that follow. We also included data from ISP partners and others such as the USFWS San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge Complex, California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW), East Bay Regional Park District, and Point Blue Conservation Science (CDFW 2016 and 2017, Elrod and Wood 2016, Estrella 2019, Liu *et al* 2009 and 2012, and Wood and Elrod 2017).

The USFWS San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge Complex completed a biological opinion in 2018 for the ISP project (2018 Biological Opinion; USFWS File No: SFBNWRC-2018-ISP-01), which supercedes the 2012 Biological Opinion. As stated above and explained below, information from the 2012 Biological Opinion was used for this 5-year review because it falls within our period of analysis. The 2018 Biological Opinion was completed after the breeding season in 2018, so any data collected or reported pursuant to the 2018 Biological Opinion falls after of our time period of analysis and is not included here. Information from implementation of the 2018 Biological Opinion will be reviewed as part of the next 5-year review for this species.

This survey data was collected from up to approximately 191 sites comprising approximately 26,200 acres of habitat. A few caveats to the data and how we used it include:

- The ISP and its partners provide habitat suitability information and conduct standardized annual California clapper rail call-count surveys required for project sites under the 2012 Biological Opinion; the project does not estimate range-wide abundance, status, or distribution for the rail population or habitat. As described in H.T. Harvey and Associates *et al* (2012), potential California clapper rail habitat area was calculated from heads-up digitizing in GIS of site/sub-area boundaries by clapper rail biologists experienced with site-specific conditions, with exclusion of unvegetated areas or habitat unsuitable for clapper rail use (e.g., open mudflats, rip rap).
- Much of the ISP rail data uses the site-sum of the highest minimum counts from three rounds of surveys per season from each survey location at a site. Survey locations are

from stations along transects within a portion of a site rather than a plotting of stations that cover an entire site. The highest minimum count is derived from the range of detections for each survey round, where each type of detection represents a standardized range of individual clapper rails (e.g., a clatter represents one-two birds and a duet represents two birds). The ranges are summed for each round and the highest number from the round with the highest minimum count is used to determine the final number of rails detected for each site for the season.

- Because the use of call playback during surveys increases the probability of detection, per Nur *et al* (2016), and as explained in USFWS (2017), we adjusted survey results accordingly by adding 18 percent to the number of detections when playback protocol was used differently than prescribed in the 2012 Biological Opinion.
- It is also noted that the ISP included fewer sites in earlier years, and across years survey methods and coverage were not entirely consistent and changes were made to site grouping/splitting and naming/numbering. For these reasons, the total number of sites and acres reported has varied over the reporting period. For the data we used, beginning in 2010 the acreage for the total number of sites remained consistent because we maintained consistent site grouping/splitting and naming/numbering.

Relative to the description above, we believe the ISP habitat information and survey data provide a relatively consistent data set for the project sites and therefore are appropriate for use as indices of both site-level and range-wide changes in rail population abundance and habitat suitability. We used the call count data as an index/estimate of annual rail abundance and trend at surveyed sites and the habitat assessment information as an index/estimate of trend for the area of habitat described as suitable for surveyed sites. We did not attempt to estimate or model rail densities or abundance for unsurveyed areas. Accordingly, because the call count surveys and habitat assessments did not include all possible habitat, we consider our estimates of population abundance and habitat area to be minimum estimates and actual population abundance is likely higher.

Comparing our Index Results to Previously Published Modeled Estimates

To evaluate the robustness of our methods, we compared our results to those from recent published modeled abundance estimates by Liu *et al* (2009), which, as mentioned above, is referenced in the 2013 5-Year Review and the Recovery Plan, and Liu *et al* (2012).

- Liu *et al* (2009) estimated annual average rail abundance for 2005-2008 at 181 sites (the report narrative states 180 sites, but *Table 1* of the report lists 181 sites), representing approximately 29,122 acres of suitable habitat. They estimated a minimum average population of 1,426 rails between 2005 and 2008. They used California clapper rail survey results to model estimated densities for entire survey sites, including un-surveyed portions of the sites. They did not model population estimates for sites that were not surveyed for rails. They did not estimate changes in the amount of suitable habitat or the amount of suitable habitat that was unoccupied by site or for a region.

- Liu *et al* (2012) estimated annual average rail abundance for 2009-2011 at 212 sites, representing approximately 32,751 acres of suitable habitat. They estimated a minimum average population of 1,046 rails between 2009 and 2011. Their rail survey data sources included the ISP data set, and respective site habitat acreage estimates were consistent with those cited in the ISP data. They used California clapper rail survey results from 159 sites with detections to model estimated densities for entire survey sites, including un-surveyed portions of the sites. They also used the survey site-modeled densities to estimate densities for an additional 53 sites without detections, but that contained what was considered suitable habitat. The report did not specify estimated densities for un-surveyed habitat or sites without detections at a site level, but rather summarized those estimates for complexes/regions. Additionally, they used their revised modeling and estimation methods to re-estimate the range-wide abundance for 2005-2008 that they had previously published in 2009 (Liu *et al* 2009) to extrapolate a range-wide abundance estimate for 2005-2011. They did not specify estimated changes in the amount of suitable habitat or the amount of suitable habitat that was unoccupied by site or for a region between the time periods (2005-2008 and 2009-2011).

The differences between our methods and those of Liu *et al* (2009 and 2012) do not allow for direct site-by-site, acre-by-acre, or region-by-region comparison. Rather, Table 1 shows a side-by-side proportional comparison of our 2005-2008 and 2009-2011 estimated average population abundance index values from direct call count results to the modeled estimated average population abundance from Liu *et al* (2009) and Liu *et al* (2012) by recovery unit, respectively. The table also shows the proportion of the Liu *et al* (2009 and 2012) model values for acreage and California clapper rail abundance represented by the respective USFWS index values to illustrate the differences between the values for each method. Because our method included less habitat area and did not include modeled rail densities for un-surveyed portions of sites or sites without detections, it is expected that our estimates of rail abundance should be lower than the Liu *et al* (2009 and 2012) estimates. Additionally, it is noted that the difference in results is more pronounced in the 2005-2008 time period than in the 2009-2011 time period, which is also expected since the coverage area (number of sites and associated acres) was more variable during 2005-2008 and became consistent during 2009-2011. Relative to these limitations, we believe that the comparison in Table 1 illustrates that our use of the population abundance index from direct call count results is sufficient for estimating a minimum population abundance and spatial distribution in this 5-year review.

Table 1 Side-by-side comparison of the 2005-2008 (top) and 2009-2011 (bottom) USFWS estimated average California clapper rail (CCR) population size index from direct call count results to the modeled estimated average population abundance from Liu *et al* (2009 and 2012), by recovery unit.

2005-2008	USFWS estimated average index, San Pablo Bay Recovery Unit	USFWS estimated average index, Central/South SF Bay Recovery Unit	USFWS estimated average index, Suisun Bay Recovery Unit	USFWS estimated average index, Total	Liu <i>et al</i> (2009) modeled estimated average, San Pablo Bay Recovery Unit	Liu <i>et al</i> (2009) modeled estimated average, Central/South SF Bay Recovery Unit	Liu <i>et al</i> (2009) modeled estimated average, Suisun Bay Recovery Unit	Liu <i>et al</i> (2009) modeled estimated average, Total	Proportion of Liu <i>et al</i> (2009) "Total" value represented by USFWS "Total" value
Approx. acreage	2,036	5,561	3,760	11,357	11,444	9,247	8,430	29,121	0.39
CCR abundance	148	740	2	890	482	934	10	1,426	0.62

2005-2008	USFWS estimated average index, San Pablo Bay Recovery Unit	USFWS estimated average index, Central/South SF Bay Recovery Unit	USFWS estimated average index, Suisun Bay Recovery Unit	USFWS estimated average index, Total	Liu <i>et al</i> (2009) modeled estimated average, San Pablo Bay Recovery Unit	Liu <i>et al</i> (2009) modeled estimated average, Central/South SF Bay Recovery Unit	Liu <i>et al</i> (2009) modeled estimated average, Suisun Bay Recovery Unit	Liu <i>et al</i> (2009) modeled estimated average, Total	Proportion of Liu <i>et al</i> (2009) "Total" value represented by USFWS "Total" value
Rails/acre	0.07	0.13	0.00	0.08	0.04	0.10	0.00	0.05	1.60

2009-2011	USFWS estimated average index, San Pablo Bay Recovery Unit	USFWS estimated average index, Central/South SF Bay Recovery Unit	USFWS estimated average index, Suisun Bay Recovery Unit	USFWS estimated average index, Total	Liu <i>et al</i> (2012) modeled estimated average, San Pablo Bay Recovery Unit	Liu <i>et al</i> (2012) modeled estimated average, Central/South SF Bay Recovery Unit	Liu <i>et al</i> (2012) modeled estimated average, Suisun Bay Recovery Unit	Liu <i>et al</i> (2012) modeled estimated average, Total	Proportion of Liu <i>et al</i> (2012) "Total" value represented by USFWS "Total" value
Approx. acreage	9,622	10,063	3,923	23,608	21,629	10,660	462	32,751	0.72
CCR abundance	237	568	1	806	501	544	1	1,046	0.77
Rails/acre	0.02	0.06	0.00	0.03	0.02	0.05	0.00	0.03	0.99

Hereafter, our estimates of population size, abundance, and trend, refer to our index. We also believe that while using the habitat assessment information from the sites in our dataset only represents a subset of potentially available habitat, it does speak to changes in habitat suitability for those sites and is appropriate in the absence of a more robust range-wide habitat assessment data set.

Population Spatial Distribution and Abundance

In our discussion about population spatial distribution and abundance below, while we mention and illustrate some population information for the time period beginning in 2005, the majority of our review is for the time period of 2010-2018. For example, several factors including predator management, tidal marsh restoration, expansion of non-native *Spartina* which provided dense cover for nesting and high tide refuge, and increased surveys are attributed to the increase and peak of the rail population in 2006-2007 (USFWS 2013a and 2013b, Lampert *et al* 2014, Overton *et al* 2014, Overton *et al* 2015, and Casazza *et al* 2016). These same references also review that while a number of factors are responsible for declines in the rail population between 2005 and 2012, a significant factor is invasive *Spartina* control, as documented by the negative relationship between effects to habitat from that activity (the short term removal of habitat provided by invasive *Spartina* and its hybrids) and the rail population. It is noted that invasive *Spartina* control is predominantly conducted in the Central/South San Francisco Bay. It is unknown if weather factors, such as storms, affect rail abundance or survey success. Additionally and related to this last point, we make some reference to the influence of habitat condition on rail distribution and abundance. In particular, we note apparent differences in rail distribution and abundance relative to changes in habitat character resulting from ISP activities. Historical population trends for the period preceding 2010 are discussed in detail in the 2013 5-Year Review and the Recovery Plan and those documents should be consulted for more information about earlier population trends. Details about ISP activities and resulting changes in habitat are

not discussed in this section, but rather in the following *Habitat Spatial Distribution and Abundance* section.

Range-wide Population Distribution and Abundance, by Recovery Unit

Overall, the estimated range-wide California clapper rail population has increased since the 2013 5-Year Review. The 2013 5-Year Review and Recovery Plan referenced the Liu *et al* (2009) estimated an average population of 1,426 rails between 2005 and 2008 (for comparison, our currently estimated average for the same time period was 890 rails; Table 1). Our estimated range-wide annual population for 2011 was 899 rails and for 2018 was 1,192 rails (Table 2, Figure 1).

At a recovery unit scale, the increase since 2011 in population estimate was observed in both the San Pablo Bay and Central/South San Francisco Bay Units (Table 2, Figure 1). The San Pablo Bay Recovery Unit had some increase in rail numbers between 2011 and 2018, with 290 birds in 2011 and 353 birds in 2018, but ended the time period nearly slightly lower proportionately, supporting about 32 percent and 30 percent of the range-wide population in 2011 and 2018, respectively. The Central/South San Francisco Bay unit experienced a greater increase in rail numbers between 2011 and 2018, with 607 birds in 2011 and 839 birds in 2018. The proportion of the range-wide population in the Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Unit also increased slightly, supporting about 67 percent and 70 percent of the range-wide population in 2011 and 2018, respectively. The Suisun Bay Recovery Unit did not experience an increase, with rail counts in that unit remaining at or near zero for the entire data series (Table 2). It is noted that establishment of sustainable populations in the Suisun Bay Unit at levels prescribed in the Recovery Plan may be considered indicative of the species occupying its full range under optimal habitat and population conditions (Service 2013a, 2013b). Because the Suisun Bay Unit has had only a few individuals recorded in intermittent years, it is generally not discussed within the text or illustrated in figures and tables in the following sections.

Table 2. Estimated annual California clapper rail abundance, 2005-2018, by recovery unit

Recovery Unit	California clapper rail annual call count totals													
	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
San Pablo Bay	165	142	126	159	151	271	290	304	243	309	310	383	388	353
Central/South San Francisco Bay	579	908	902	570	543	554	607	560	482	509	603	618	720	839
Suisun Bay	0	5	0	1	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	744	1,055	1,027	730	694	825	899	863	725	818	913	1,001	1,108	1,192

Figure 1. Estimated annual California clapper rail population size (top) and proportion (bottom) 2005-2018, for the San Pablo Bay and Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Units.

We also calculated a 10-year average population index by recovery unit to measure progress toward Recovery Criterion E/1 downlisting threshold values (Table 3). Recovery Criterion E/1 addresses Factor E (other natural or manmade factors affecting a species continued existence) of the five-factors. Criterion E/1 establishes minimum 10-year average population sizes, by recovery unit, to demonstrate that criteria under Factors A-C (A-present or threatened destruction, modification, or curtailment of habitat or range; B-overutilization for commercial, recreational, scientific, or educational purposes; and C-disease or predation) have been sufficiently met to provide resilience to stochastic events over a large geographic area. As shown in Table 4, our estimated 10-year average population for 2009-2018 falls short of the Recovery Criterion E/1 downlisting threshold for each recovery unit. Because the 10-year average population values fell so far short of the Recovery Criterion E/1 downlisting thresholds, we did not evaluate progress toward other downlisting criteria.

Table 3. Estimated California clapper rail 10-year average population and proportion of downlisting criterion E/1 achieved, for 2009-2018, by recovery unit.

	San Pablo Bay Recovery Unit	Central/South SF Bay Recovery Unit	Suisun Bay Recovery Unit
Recovery Plan 10-year average population downlisting criterion (E/1) minimum threshold	936	1,060	100
2009-2018 10-year average population estimate	306	617	0
2009-2018 proportion of criterion achieved	0.33	0.58	0.00

Population Distribution and Abundance, between and within Recovery Units

We looked at differences in population distribution and abundance within recovery units to try to understand any changes in ecosystem or habitat function between certain sites and regions. Because of the removal of high density cover which provides nesting and high tide refuge habitat, and the known negative effects to habitat and the rail population from invasive *Spartina* treatments (see the *Habitat Spatial Distribution and Abundance* and *Habitat Degradation and Disturbance: Invasive Spartina Control* sections, below), we compared rail counts in the Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Unit at 10 sites (547 acres) closed to invasive *Spartina* treatment beginning in 2012 and until certain thresholds were met, compared to 150 sites (10,103 acres) that were not closed to treatment. In general, between 2012 and 2018, the population estimate in the Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Unit increased at sites closed to treatment and decreased at sites where treatment was allowed. An exception to this is reflected in the call count totals for 2018. In 2018, the San Pablo Bay Unit had 353 rails, a nine percent decrease from the year prior and following five consecutive years of increasing numbers, the Central/South San Francisco Bay Unit sites open to invasive *Spartina* treatment had 555 rails, a 13 percent increase from the year prior and the highest number since 2007, and the Central/South San Francisco Bay Unit sites closed to invasive *Spartina* treatment had 284 rails, a 0.01 percent decrease from the year prior and following six consecutive years of increasing numbers and where 287 rails in 2017 represented the highest number since 2007. It is noted that for the 150 sites where treatment is allowed, not every site is treated in every year and since the data is aggregated, it is not possible to understand the factors that may have influenced the change in 2018 without additional information and analysis. The next 5-year review will provide a good opportunity for that further analysis. Relative to the current analysis and in comparison to the closed and open sites in the Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Unit, in the San Pablo Bay Recovery Unit (31 sites and 11,623 acres), where no sites were closed to treatment for comparison, the population estimate generally increased between 2012 and 2018 (Table 4, Figure 2).

As a proportion of the range-wide population, the sites closed to treatment experienced the greatest increase, supporting about 12 percent of the range-wide population in 2012 and 24 percent of the range-wide population in 2018 (Figure 2). In comparison, the proportion of the range-wide population from sites where treatment was allowed decreased during the same time period, declining from about 53 percent to 46 percent of the range-wide population in 2012 and 2018, respectively (Figure 2). In the San Pablo Bay Recovery Unit, the unit’s contribution to the

range-wide population also declined from 35 percent in 2012 to 30 percent in 2018 (Table 4, Figure 2).

Table 4. Estimated annual California clapper rail abundance, by recovery unit. The red line indicates when respective sites were closed to treatment (2012).

Recovery Unit	California clapper rail annual call count totals													
	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
San Pablo Bay	165	142	126	159	151	271	290	304	243	309	310	383	388	353
Central/South San Francisco Bay, sites not closed in 2012 to invasive <i>Spartina</i> treatment	412	680	600	347	402	435	494	458	391	406	440	411	433	555
Central/South San Francisco Bay, sites closed in 2012 to invasive <i>Spartina</i> treatment	168	228	302	223	142	119	113	102	91	103	163	207	287	284
Suisun Bay	0	5	0	1	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	744	1,055	1,027	730	694	825	899	863	725	818	913	1,001	1,108	1,192

Figure 2. Estimated annual California clapper rail population size (top) and proportion (bottom) 2005-2018, for the San Pablo Bay, Central/South San Francisco Bay (sites closed to invasive *Spartina*

treatment in 2012), and Central/South San Francisco Bay (sites not closed to invasive *Spartina* treatment in 2012) Recovery Units. The red line indicates when respective sites were closed to treatment (2012).

Our analysis above suggests that while the California clapper rail population appears to have increased across both the San Pablo Bay and Central/South San Francisco Recovery Units since the 2013 5-Year Review, the distribution of rails has become increasingly concentrated to fewer sites and less habitat area. For example, the proportionately increased importance of the 10 sites in the Central/South San Francisco Bay (547 acres) closed to invasive *Spartina* treatment beginning in 2012 is clear. Additionally, spatial distribution and population thresholds prescribed in downlisting criterion E/1 for a specified average number of rails over a 10-year period by recovery unit (USFWS 2013b) have not been achieved. The sections below include more analysis and discussion about the relationship between the rail population and habitat distribution and abundance.

Habitat Spatial Distribution and Abundance

As briefly discussed above, we looked at reported changes in site-level habitat suitability at survey sites to try to understand possible relationships with changes in the California clapper rail population spatial distribution and abundance. In this section, we discuss this in greater detail.

The reported changes in habitat suitability we considered came from site-specific assessments conducted in a given year, as rail surveys were discontinued at sites when habitat was described as no longer suitable, or as rail surveys detected no rails. We reviewed data for the San Pablo Bay and Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Units from 2010-2018 because overall acreage estimates were the most consistent during this period (see *Methods*, above). As explained above in the *Population Spatial Distribution and Abundance* section, we did not include the Suisun Bay Recovery Unit in this analysis because it has never supported large or consistent number of rails.

In general, we expect a positive relationship between the amount of reported suitable habitat and the size of the rail population, but this is not what we found between 2010 and 2018. Overall for the time period of 2010-2018 (in the San Pablo Bay and Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Units combined), we observed a trend where the rail population increased, while the amount of reported suitable habitat/unsurveyed acreage decreased or remained unchanged. By recovery unit, in the San Pablo Bay Unit, the population increase appears to mostly accompany a decrease in the amount of suitable habitat/unsurveyed acreage, with the possible exception of 2018, when almost no unsuitable habitat was reported, but there was a significant increase in the acreage of unsurveyed sites. The Central/South San Francisco Bay Unit experienced a more dramatic decrease in the amount of suitable habitat/surveyed acreage until 2017, when there was an increase in the acreage of sites not surveyed, and still exhibited an increase in rail abundance. In 2018, the continued increase in rail numbers and acreage of sites surveyed is encouraging, but may be at least partly explained by more acreage being surveyed.

Recently, several new marsh restoration projects in the South Bay have occurred such as Island Ponds in Alviso, parts of Eden Landing, and as of 2020, a portion of Outer Bair Island. The South Bay Salt Pond Restoration Project has projects that are starting this year. In the North Bay,

the Dixon and Cullinan Ranch restoration projects have been initiated. At Sonoma Creek marsh, marsh/upland ecotones were built as well as high tide refuge islands. Past restoration projects include Lower Tubbs, Tolay Creek, and Sonoma Baylands (Albertson 2020). The relationship of this restored habitat and any effect it has on rail populations will be explored in the future.

As mentioned in the previous section and illustrated above in Table 4 and Figures 2, 3, and 4, the inverted habitat area:population estimate relationship may be at least partly explained by the implementation of management practices to minimize effects to the rail from invasive *Spartina* control activities, including closing some sites to treatment beginning in 2012. The ISP began in 2000, with the most aggressive and widespread eradication efforts during 2005-2009. The project employs several control strategies, including the use of herbicides, and the severity of habitat structure impacts from invasive *Spartina* control using certain herbicides is delayed for one-two growing seasons after treatment as treated plants break down, which results in a lag of several breeding seasons before impacts to local rail populations are reflected in survey results. Table 3 and Figure 2 show the overall population decline in the years around 2008-2009 and the sustained decline in the Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Unit through 2014 where the majority of invasive *Spartina* control has taken place as compared to the San Pablo Bay Recovery Unit, where the least invasive *Spartina* control took place because little was present.

Figure 4 shows specifically the difference in rail population trend in the Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Unit where 10 sites were closed to invasive *Spartina* treatment beginning in 2012 as compared to the other 150 sites that were not closed to treatment. The chart for 2005-2018 illustrates that the 10 sites closed to invasive *Spartina* treatment in 2012 supported a large proportion of the rail population prior to the effects of treatment becoming evident (which is why they were selected for closure) and support an increasing proportion of the Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Unit, and range-wide, population since closure. Also as illustrated in the 2005-2018 chart, and mentioned above in the *Methods* section, the number of sites and acreage included in our data set increased from 2005 and became consistent beginning in 2010.

From a recovery unit and range-wide perspective, the 10 sites that were closed to invasive *Spartina* treatment in 2012 represent about 547 acres (five percent) of our estimated 10,650 acres of habitat at the 160 sites in the Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Unit and about two percent of our estimated 26,200 acres of habitat at the 191 sites in the San Pablo Bay, Central/South San Francisco Bay, and Suisun Bay Recovery Units, combined. In 2018, these 10 sites (547 acres or five percent of recovery unit habitat and two percent of range-wide habitat) supported about 34 percent of Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Unit population and about 24 percent of the range-wide population. It is noted that a new biological opinion for the ISP project was issued by the San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge Complex of the USFWS in 2018 (USFWS File No: SFBNWRC-2018-ISP-01). According to that biological opinion, the ISP began re-introducing invasive *Spartina* control activities at some of the sites that were closed to treatment in 2012, following the California clapper rail breeding season in 2018 (Olofson Environmental, Inc. 2018; USFWS 2018).

Overall, the relationships illustrated in Table 4 and Figures 2, 3, and 4, and discussed above, suggest that for the sites in our data set, less habitat is supporting more rails in 2018 as compared to 2010. The next 5-year review will provide an opportunity to see if the rail population increases

continue and to further evaluate the relationship between habitat and rail spatial distribution and abundance, including possible effects from management activities including invasive *Spartina* control.

Figure 3. Estimated acreage of sites with unsuitable habitat and/or no rails, not surveyed, and with >0 rails, and California clapper rail abundance, 2010-2018, for the Central/South San Francisco Bay and San Pablo Bay Recovery Units combined (top), San Pablo Bay Recovery Unit (center), and the Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Unit (bottom). Relative to habitat suitability reports, while in a given year of project monitoring some sites may not be surveyed for a variety of reasons, for the acreage-type classes in Figure 3, it is noted that there is some overlap of the “sites with unsuitable habitat and/or 0 rails” and “unsurveyed sites” because surveys are often simply discontinued at many sites once the habitat has been described as unsuitable and the reason for not surveying a site is not always reported.

Figure 4. Estimated California clapper rail abundance for the acreage of sites with >0 rails that were not closed to treatment in 2012 and the acreage of sites closed to treatment in 2012 (all with >0 rails), for 2005-2018 (top) and for 2010-2018 (bottom), in the Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Unit. The red line indicates when sites were closed to treatment (2012).

New Information about Threats Relative to Respective Listing Factors

The 2013 5-Year Review enumerated the extant threats under respective listing factors (Five Factors) outlined in section 4(a)(1) of the Act. All of the threats discussed in the 2013 5-Year Review continue to act on the California clapper rail. Since the 2013 5-Year Review and Recovery Plan were completed, new information about some threats has become available and is discussed below. All factors and threats from the 2013 5-Year Review are listed below; however, only those factors and threats for which new information was available are discussed here and it is noted below if no new information for a factor or threat was available to us for this review. Specifically, new information about ecotones, invasive *Spartina* control, sea-level rise, mercury contamination, and within- and across-population genetic diversity is summarized below. This new information further informs our understanding of these threats.

Factor A: Present or Threatened Destruction, Modification, or Curtailment of Habitat or Range

Habitat Loss and Fragmentation

Habitat Loss:

As explained above, several new marsh restoration projects in the South Bay have occurred such as Island Ponds in Alviso, parts of Eden Landing, and as of 2020, a portion of Outer Bair Island. The South Bay Salt Pond Restoration Project has projects that are starting this year. In the North Bay, the Dixon and Cullinan Ranch restoration projects have been initiated. At Sonoma Creek marsh, marsh/upland ecotones were built as well as high tide refuge islands. Past restoration projects include Lower Tubbs, Tolay Creek, and Sonoma Baylands (Albertson 2020).

Habitat Fragmentation and Edge Effects

No new information was available for this review.

Habitat Degradation and Disturbance

Levees

No new information was available for this review.

Loss of Ecotones

Nur et al (2018) evaluated the wildlife benefit of upland transition zone habitat features in habitat restorations. They found that increasing plant canopy height and density, grass cover, and width of the transition zone were beneficial—resulting in positive rail population trends.

Disturbance

No new information was available for this review.

Salinity Changes

No new information was available for this review.

Invasive Species and Invasive Species Control

Invasive *Spartina* Control

The 2013 5-Year Review, Recovery Plan, Lampert *et al* (2014), Overton *et al* (2014), Overton *et al* (2015), and Casazza *et al* (2016) explain that the expansion of invasive *Spartina* across the San Francisco Bay is correlated with an increase in California clapper rail survival and rail population numbers into the early 2000s. These references also review that a number of factors are responsible for declines in the rail population, and the greatest influence since about 2005 is considered to be the negative relationship between invasive *Spartina* control and the rail population. For example, Casazza *et al* (2016) performed a meta-analysis of annual California clapper rail and invasive *Spartina* surveys and estimated that rail populations throughout San Francisco Bay declined nine percent per year between 2005 and 2012, but declines were stronger where the most invasive *Spartina* treatment occurred. Cumulative change in the amount of invasive *Spartina* within a marsh was a better predictor of rail population change than year-to-year invasive *Spartina* changes. California clapper rail populations at sites not invaded by *Spartina* were estimated to have declined at an annual rate of three percent per year between 2005 and 2012. In comparison, at invaded sites, every two and one-half percent reduction in the marsh surface that was subject to invasive *Spartina* removal was associated with an additional one percent decline in subsequent rail population growth rates.

Our current analysis also illustrates the negative relationship between invasive *Spartina* control and the rail population. In the *Population Spatial Distribution and Abundance* section above, we explain the difference in rail population trend between sites open and closed to invasive *Spartina* control. For example, the Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Unit sites that were closed to invasive *Spartina* treatment in 2012 supported about 12 percent and 24 percent of the range-wide population in 2011 and 2018, respectively. By comparison, the Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Unit sites that were open to Invasive *Spartina* treatment supported about 53 percent and 46 percent of the range-wide population in 2011 and 2018, respectively. There is an evident pattern that the modest overall increase in abundance has been associated predominantly with the areas that have been closed to treatment during this time interval.

Despite negative impacts to California clapper rail populations, invasive *Spartina* control is considered beneficial to many tidal marsh species and their habitat and the ISP section 7 consultation process is used to adaptively implement invasive *Spartina* control while minimizing effects to the rail. For example, in addition to closing some sites to invasive *Spartina* control, the 2012 Biological Opinion required habitat enhancement and restoration concurrent with invasive *Spartina* eradication activities. To date, ISP habitat enhancements include construction of 60 high tide refuge islands to provide rails cover from predators in marshes where high cover has been determined to be limited. In addition, there has been extensive revegetation of both *Grindelia stricta* (gumplant) and *Spartina foliosa* (Pacific cordgrass) plantings to increase habitat diversity and cover (Olofson Environmental, Inc. 2018). Related to such adaptive management, research is ongoing into California clapper rail habitat restoration and enhancement strategies to offset impacts from invasive *Spartina* control. Some information gained since the 2013 5-Year Review is summarized below.

Lampert *et al* (2014) proposed a three-stage management strategy that included (1) eradication of invasive *Spartina* until rail habitat constraints are limiting, at which point further removal is prohibited; (2) native *Spartina* is replanted until coverage and structure is sufficient to support

the rail again; and (3) remaining invasive *Spartina* is slowly removed. However, this “overlapping” strategy where native *Spartina* would be planted before invasive *Spartina* is eradicated may not adequately address some managers’ concerns regarding hybridization between the invasive *S. alterniflora* and the native *S. foliosa*.

Overton *et al* (2014) also advocated for management that balances the loss of beneficial non-native habitat provided by the invasive *Spartina* with maintaining adjacent native habitat, especially with respect to rail survival during tidal flooding. They suggest that high quality habitat should include both short term (3–5 hour), and seasonal (3–4 months) tidal refuge cover, as limitations in these features following treatment likely reflect a bottleneck in annual survival rates for the species.

Overton *et al* (2015) demonstrated some success with the use of floating artificial islands to provide high tide refugial habitat. Their study found that when tide levels inundated the marsh plain, use of artificial islands was at least 300 times more frequent than would be expected if California clapper rails used artificial habitats. The probability of use varied among islands, and low levels of use were observed at night. They propose that artificial habitats, such as the supplemental escape cover provided by floating man-made islands, may provide effective short-term mitigation for habitat losses resulting from activities such as invasive *Spartina* control, and events such as sea-level rise.

In addition to performing meta-analysis of rail and invasive *Spartina* survey results (mentioned above), Casazza *et al* (2016) offered ecosystem management planning recommendations to prevent unintended consequences from the implementation of conflicting management goals (e.g., the unintended negative consequences to the rail from invasive *Spartina* control):

- Start with coordinated and assimilated desired future conditions, develop best/alternative management actions, describe how actions fit into ecosystem management plans; and develop a consensus regarding the current state of knowledge for the topic at hand.
- Establish a clear consensus on baseline conditions or thresholds that will trigger management changes. These thresholds may include effects directly caused by intervention actions (e.g., direct take or mortality of individuals); those indirectly caused by subsequent change to habitat or ecological processes (e.g., indirect take through harassment or habitat change); or even population trends caused by factors entirely outside the scope of interventions (e.g., climate-induced population declines or stochastic events).
- Identify information needed to support alternative management actions (e.g., risk assessments and resource and implementation monitoring), and establish funding and timeline to initiate projects.
- Use phased projects and evaluation of intermediate conditions, or necessary preconditions that require additional intervention (i.e., what works in one area may not in another).
- Consider innovative methods and materials (e.g., artificial habitats, assisted migration, captive breeding, and intensive predator control).

- Quantify both negative effects and benefits to other ecosystem components for risk evaluation.
- Make use of collaboration and data sharing with common minimum standards and methods with consensus-driven interpretation and implication of findings.

Julian Wood *et al* (2017) assessed the benefit to California clapper rails from constructed high tide refuge mounds and high-density planting enhancements implemented as part of the ISP habitat restoration program. Their assessment suggested there may be limited benefit via such management tools to rails at a subset of sites evaluated, but results were largely inconclusive across the entire study. They recommended further evaluation with additional years of data.

The USFWS San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge Complex noted that the high tide refuge mounds are one of many restoration elements they incorporate into their tidal marsh restorations (Albertson 2020).

Lepidium latifolium

No new information was available for this review.

Invertebrates

No new information was available for this review.

Conservation

No new information was available for this review.

Combined Factors

No new information was available for this review.

Factor B: Overutilization for Commercial, Recreational, Scientific, or Educational Purposes

No new information was available for this review.

Factor C: Disease or Predation

Disease

No new information was available for this review.

Predation

No new information was available for this review.

Factor D: Inadequacy of Existing Regulatory Mechanisms

Federal Protections

No new information was available for this review.

State and Local Protections

No new information was available for this review.

Factor E: Other Natural or Manmade Factors Affecting Its Continued Existence

Global Warming and Climate Change:

Sea-Level Rise

In the 2013 5-Year Review, the local effect of sea-level rise associated with global climate change, was identified as the most central threat to the long-term survival of the California clapper rail. Sea-level rise (SLR) is expected to increasingly threaten California clapper rail tidal marsh habitat extent and condition (Zhang and Gorelick 2014, Rosencranz *et al* 2018, Thorne *et al* 2018, Thorne *et al* 2019). Considerable research has been conducted to model effects of potential sea-level rise to coastal and estuarine habitat, including for the rail. Some information that has become available since the 2013 5-Year Review is summarized below.

Zhang and Gorelick (2014) evaluated the potential effectiveness of regionally planned restoration activities for offsetting California clapper rail habitat impacts from SLR. They found the most influential factors that characterize the quality of rail tidal marsh habitat are salinity, which is a proxy for higher quality nesting environment and abundance of macroinvertebrates, and tidal conditions, which affect flood and predation threats. In addition to a no restoration scenario, three restoration scenarios were considered over a time course to 2060: Plan 1 (sub-regional conservative) to restore 35 marshes (over 7,507 acres [ac]); Plan 2 (sub-regional aggressive) to restore 52 marshes (over 13,512 ac); and Plan 3 (Estuary-wide) to restore 232 marshes (over 43,535 ac). Three SLR scenarios were also considered; low (42 centimeter [cm]; 17 inches [in]), moderate (92 cm; 36 in), and high (166 cm; 65 in) SLR.

Without restoration, they estimated eight percent and 66 percent loss of present-day habitat, and one percent and 36 percent risk of extinction, under moderate and high SLR scenarios, respectively. Their modeled results suggest that with either restoration plan, rail viability should remain at the present level under moderate SLR. Under high SLR, the risk of extinction decreases from 26 percent under either Plans 1 or 2 to 20 percent under Plan 3. Also under high SLR, they noted that habitat contributions from restoration become quite limited, where the fraction of high-quality habitat is expected to decrease under all restoration plans, even though the area of marsh increases, which suggests that the majority of currently restored marshes do not provide conditions to support high-quality habitat in the future.

Compared with sub-regional efforts, Zhang and Gorelick (2014) found that estuary-wide conservation would be more effective for improving reproduction and dispersal success and accommodating sea-level rise of an additional 10 cm (3.9 in) before the population falls below criticality. They defined population criticality by two types: 1) when the risk of decline to 25 surviving females reaches 50 percent; and 2) when the expected minimum population of females becomes too small (≤ 25) to maintain demographic stochasticity and genetic diversity. Sub-regional restoration efforts would increase the *type I* critical height by 2–4 cm (0.8-1.6 in) and *type II* critical height by 2 cm (0.8 in). In comparison, Estuary-wide efforts allow sea level to rise 8–9 cm (3.2-3.5 in) without causing the bird population to fall below criticality. For the high SLR scenario, the extinction risk would be reduced by 28 percent with sub-regional schemes and by 56 percent under the Estuary-wide scheme. They also concluded that should sea level rise to the predicted maximum of 190 cm (74.8 in), proposed conservation efforts are likely to be ineffective in preventing rail extinction by 2100.

Rosencranz *et al* (2018) evaluated how site-specific differences in ecogeomorphic processes (interactions between organisms and the development of landforms) may result in different SLR vulnerabilities over time for the *Rallus longirostris* complex that includes the California clapper rail (*R. l. obsoletus*), the Light-footed clapper rail (*R. l. levipes*), and the Yuma clapper rail (*R. l. yumanensis*) across California. Salt marsh vulnerabilities to SLR were forecasted across a total of 14 study sites (11 sites were California clapper rail habitat in the San Francisco Bay; Figure 5) using two models. They used a Wetland Accretion Rate Model of Ecosystem Resilience (WARMER) model to account for changes in above and belowground marsh processes and MaxEnt modelling software, which uses elevation and distance to tide creek and California clapper rail presence-only occurrence data to predict an index of habitat suitability. Under a high (166 cm; 65.7 in/100 yr) SLR scenario, current extent of suitable habitat was projected to increase by 34 percent across the combined area of 14 sites by 2050, but by 2100, total habitat suitability is projected to decrease by 83 percent, with six salt marshes losing over 95 percent of suitable habitat. Under a high SLR scenario, San Francisco Bay's suitable habitat is predicted to increase by 35 percent at midcentury, but by 2100, San Francisco Bay is forecasted to lose 84 percent of suitable habitat. If accretion rates cannot keep pace with SLR, salt marsh-obligate species are in danger of being extirpated from their habitat. Figure 5 illustrates the percent of suitable habitat changes projected under the three SLR scenarios out to 2110 in San Francisco Bay.

Figure 5. Modeled percent suitable California clapper rail habitat changes through time across three sea level rise scenarios (SLR) (blue line = 44 cm (17.3 in) SLR; red line = 93 cm (36.6 in) SLR; black line = 166 cm (65.4 in) SLR) in 11 California salt marsh sites in San Francisco Bay. Salt marsh modeling results are ordered by geographic region from north (top) to south (bottom) (Figure from Rosencranz *et al* 2018).

Thorne *et al* (2108) used a comprehensive scenario approach to evaluate both the vertical and horizontal response of tidal wetlands to projected changes in the rate of SLR across 14 estuaries along the Pacific coast of the continental United States through 2110 (Figure 6). Throughout the U.S. Pacific region, they found that tidal wetlands are highly vulnerable to end-of-century submergence, with resulting extensive loss of habitat. The SLR values for each scenario varied by region; SLR values for California were, low (+44 cm; 17.3 in), moderate (+93 cm; 36.6 in), and high (+166 cm; 65.4 in). Using higher-range SLR scenarios, all high and middle marsh habitats were lost, with 83 percent of current tidal wetlands transitioning to unvegetated habitats by 2110. The projected high and middle marsh habitat area lost was greater in California and Oregon (100 percent) but still severe in Washington, with 68 percent submerged by the end of the century. The only wetland habitat remaining at the end of the century was low marsh under higher range SLR rates. Tidal wetland loss was also likely under more

conservative SLR scenarios, including loss of 95 percent of high marsh and 60 percent of middle marsh habitats by the end of the century. Horizontal migration of most wetlands was constrained by coastal development or steep topography, with just two wetland sites having sufficient upland space for migration and the possibility for nearly 1:1 replacement, making SLR threats particularly high in the Pacific region and generally undocumented, as compared to other coastal regions of the U.S. They concluded that with low vertical accretion rates and little upland migration space, Pacific coast tidal wetlands are at imminent risk of submergence with projected rates of rapid SLR. Figure 6 illustrates projected percent habitat area under the three SLR scenarios.

Additionally, Thorne *et al* (2019) found that avian predator numbers and activity in tidal marshes increased with high-tide events and that increased flooding, as is expected with sea-level rise, will increase avian predator pressure on wildlife prey, including California clapper rail. They found that there was higher predation pressure from ardeids (egrets and herons) than raptor species. Their study highlights the importance of predator–prey interactions and the amplification of predation pressure under flooded conditions, which has implications for population persistence, especially in small, fragmented habitats under sea-level rise.

Figure 6. Modeled percent habitat area projections under three SLR scenarios (SLR values for California are, low (+44 cm; 17.3 in), moderate (+93 cm; 36.6 in), and high (+166 cm; 65.4 in)). Bolinas and Petaluma are San Francisco area and Bay locations, respectively. Under moderate and high SLR scenarios, all study sites are projected to undergo substantial loss of elevation over the coming century. By 2050, under moderate and high SLR scenarios, there is a gradual loss of high marsh habitats with an expansion of middle and low marsh habitats. Under moderate SLR scenarios by 2110, there is a loss of middle and high marsh habitats and submergence of tidal marsh, with a conversion to intertidal mudflat and open water at 36% of the study sites. Under high SLR scenarios, there is a total loss of all middle and high marsh habitats and submergence at 86% of the study sites, with three study sites going partly subtidal. (Figure from Thorne *et al* 2018).

Contaminants

Mercury Contamination

As reviewed in the 2013 5-Year Review, pollutants are a threat to the estuary's aquatic and aquatic-dependent wildlife species, with the greatest risk being from contamination by bioaccumulative pollutants such as mercury (Hg) and selenium (Se). The results of some research into effects to California clapper rail and exposure risk since the 2013 5-Year Review is summarized below.

Ackerman *et al* (2012) examined Hg exposure in 133 California clapper rails from four sites across San Francisco Bay. They found that Hg concentrations among adult birds were largely attributed to site. They found mean total mercury concentrations of 0.56 micrograms/gram ($\mu\text{g/g}$) wet weight (ww) in blood (range: 0.15-1.43 $\mu\text{g/g}$), 9.87 $\mu\text{g/g}$ fresh weight (fw) in head feathers (3.37-22.0 $\mu\text{g/g}$), 9.04 $\mu\text{g/g}$ fw in breast feathers (3.68-20.0 $\mu\text{g/g}$), and 0.57 $\mu\text{g/g}$ fresh wet weight (fww) in abandoned eggs (0.15-2.70 $\mu\text{g/g}$). Overall, 15 percent of blood and 56-63 percent of feather samples from rails were over 1.0 $\mu\text{g/g}$ ww and 9.0 $\mu\text{g/g}$ fw, respectively. These Hg concentrations are considered to put birds at risk of impaired reproduction.

Although the sample size for eggs was small due to restrictions on collecting viable eggs from an endangered species, and therefore the results are subject to survivor bias (meaning the failed eggs are solely represented in the sample), they found that 31 percent of abandoned clapper rail eggs were considered at high risk (>1.0 $\mu\text{g/g}$ fww) of reproductive impairment based on toxicity endpoints for other species. They found that body condition was negatively related to Hg concentration and model-averaged estimates indicated a potential decrease in body mass of 20-22 g (5-7 percent) over the observed range of observed Hg concentrations. Their results indicate the potential for detrimental effects of Hg contamination on endangered rails in tidal marsh habitats of San Francisco Bay.

Casazza *et al* (2014) analyzed total mercury (Hg) in six macroinvertebrate and one fish species representing Clapper rail diets from the same four tidal-marshes examined by Ackerman *et al* (2012) in San Francisco Bay, California. The authors reviewed that tidal marsh habitats present inherent risk to rails via exposure to Hg for the following reasons: (1) sediments in the San Francisco Bay are highly polluted with Hg derived from historic Hg and gold mining (Davis *et al* 2012 in Casazza *et al* 2014, Donovan *et al* 2013 in Casazza *et al* 2014); and (2) the many channels and sloughs bisecting tidal marsh habitats are not only areas where rails forage, but also provide conditions for converting inorganic Hg to highly toxic and bioaccumulative methyl Hg because they experience frequent wetting and drying from tidal cycles (Marvin-DiPasquale *et al* 2003 in Casazza *et al* 2014) and have high inputs of organic matter derived from high rates of primary production (Lambertsson and Nilsson 2006 in Casazza *et al* 2014).

Casazza *et al* (2014) found Hg concentrations among individual taxa of macroinvertebrates and fish ranged from lowest at Colma Creek (mean range: 0.09–0.2 $\mu\text{g/g}$ dry weight [dw]) to highest at Cogswell (0.2–0.7 $\mu\text{g/g}$ dw), Laumeister (0.2–0.9 $\mu\text{g/g}$ dw) and Arrowhead Marshes (0.3–1.9 $\mu\text{g/g}$ dw). These spatial patterns for Hg matched patterns reported previously in Clapper Rail blood from the same four marshes by Ackerman *et al* (2012). Over 25 percent of eastern mudsnails (*Ilyanassa obsoleta*) and staghorn sculpin (*Leptocottus armatus*) exceeded dietary Hg

concentrations often associated with avian reproductive impairment. Their results indicate that Hg concentrations vary considerably among tidal-marshes and diet taxa, and Hg concentrations of prey may provide an appropriate proxy for relative exposure risk for rails.

Risk of Extirpation Due to Small Populations

Within- and Across-Population Genetic Diversity Information

Dustin Wood *et al* (2017) estimated California clapper rail genetic diversity and population structure and assessed demographic connectivity among seven tidal marshes across the San Francisco Bay. They genotyped 107 rails across 11 microsatellite loci and a single mitochondrial gene to estimate genetic diversity and population structure and assessed connectivity by inferring patterns of gene flow and migration rates.

They found pronounced genetic structuring among four geographically separate genetic clusters. Gene flow analyses supported a stepping-stone model of gene flow from south-to-north across the bay with low contemporary gene flow among the regional embayments. Genetic diversity among occupied marshes and genetic clusters were not significantly different. They detected low effective population sizes and significantly high relatedness among individuals within marshes.

Based on their analyses, they recommended that preserving genetic diversity and connectivity throughout the bay may require focus of salt marsh restoration in the Central Bay where habitat is both most limited and most fragmented. They suggested the greatest need for protection of the South Bay populations since the larger marshes of the South Bay appear to be the current source of successful migrants and the region of highest diversity in the San Francisco Bay. Additionally, they noted a need for managing the landscape to maintain a network of marshes within estimated dispersal distances to support genetic connectivity among regional embayments. Their analyses suggest that dispersal patterns for the rail are predominately successful within 5–14 kilometers (3.1–8.7 miles) of natal territories and that gene flow beyond 14 kilometers (8.7 miles) is comparatively rare or unsuccessful.

Additional within- and across-population genetic diversity research is currently taking place under the *California Ridgway's Rail (California Clapper Rail) Translocation and Monitoring Project (USFWS IAA #4500104709)* funded by the BDFWO; however, no results are available at this time.

Conclusion:

After reviewing the best available scientific information, we conclude that California clapper rail remains an endangered species. The evaluation of threats affecting the species under the factors in 4(a)(1) of the Act and analysis of the status of the species in our 2013 5-Year Review remains an accurate reflection of the species' current status. The species' status remains endangered and we did not revise the recovery priority number of 3C. The priority number of 3C is based on a high degree of threat, a high potential of recovery, and its taxonomic standing as a subspecies. The additional "C" ranking indicates some degree of conflict between the conservation needs of the species and economic development (USFWS 1983).

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE ACTIONS:

Since the time when the 2013 5-Year Review was completed, the Recovery Plan has been finalized. The Recovery Plan identifies short- and long-term components of the recovery strategy. In addition to the Recovery Plan strategies and recommendations for future actions from the 2013 5-Year Review, the following actions are recommended over the next five years:

- 1) **Develop a California clapper rail range-wide, long-term, population monitoring plan and program.** This effort would be designed to specifically address needs for evaluating the status and distribution and recovery progress of the species relative to the Recovery Plan. It will include standardized protocols for monitoring, data collection, reporting, and analysis.
- 2) **Develop standardized California clapper rail habitat assessment and modeling protocol.** Habitat assessment and modeling protocol is necessary to evaluate the suitability of habitat, estimate the extent and configuration of current habitat, and project the extent and configuration of habitat into the future. The protocol would be used in estimating rail and habitat status and distribution and measuring progress toward recovery criteria.
- 3) **Develop tidal marsh restoration guidelines, with emphasis on the Recovery Plan focal species, including California clapper rail.** The proposed tidal marsh restoration guidelines would update and expand upon the *Design Guidelines for Tidal Wetland Restoration in San Francisco Bay* (Philip Williams & Associates, Ltd. and Faber 2004). The effort should: (A) access and analyze focal species, vegetation, and topographic survey data from tidal marsh restorations and natural marshes; (B) evaluate the performance of multiple habitat and system/function measures and restoration design elements for the focal species; (C) prescribe tidal marsh restoration features and values that will best benefit the focal species into the future; (D) recommend monitoring data collection and reporting protocol and standards for evaluating the same habitat benefits to the focal species; and (E) work with all partners, including land managers, tidal marsh experts, and other interested parties

Kaylee Allen, Project Leader, San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service

Approve _____ Date _____

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